

Evaluating Continuous Usage Intentions of PromptPay in Bangkok: The Role of Perceived Trust

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Abstract

PromptPay is Thailand's payment system allowing users to transfer money via their citizen ID or mobile phone number. While it aims to be a leading national e-payment system, trust concerns have impacted users' willingness to continue using it. This study investigates the effect of perceived trust on user satisfaction, emotional engagement, and continued usage intention in Bangkok, along with the moderating role of switching barriers. Using PLS-SEM for analysis, the results show that perceived trust positively influences satisfaction and emotional engagement. Furthermore, satisfaction, emotional engagement, and switching barriers positively affect continued usage intention. Also, higher levels of education were associated with a greater tendency for continued PromptPay usage. Practical recommendations include improving user experience, enhancing trust through security, and implementing loyalty programs to drive long-term engagement.

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Keywords: perceived trust, continue usage intention, satisfaction, emotional engagement, switching barrier, e-payment, PromptPay

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1. Introduction

In our modern age, technology plays an important role in simplify many aspects of our lives. Financial technology has changed the way we handle transactions and put us on the path to become a cashless society. This shift is very pronounced in Thailand, where the government has been actively trying to promote digital payments. This has become particularly evident during the COVID19 pandemic, since during this period reducing physical contact was essential. “*PromptPay*” is one of the key financial services that has been used to drive the Thai nation to cashless society.

PromptPay has been used as a fundamental payment infrastructure that expands options for users to transfer money since 2016 (Bank of Thailand, 2023). It allows users to transfer money though digital channels by using their mobile phone number and national identification number. PromptPay service requires lower fees compared to traditional transaction methods. To use the PromptPay service, a user must register their bank account to their mobile phone number or citizen ID. However, one mobile phone number and ID number can be used to register with one account only. PromptPay comes with Thai QR payment that allows users to make payment systems easier by creating Quick Respond Code (QR Code) to receive or make a payment. Additionally, PromptPay offers a variety of services that have acquired widespread popularity across public, business, and government sector, and have led to a sustained stream of payment transactions.

The research indicates that the success of this new information technology relies on both initial adoption and continued usage (Puriwat & Tripopsakul, 2021). Emphasizing the importance of continued usage, the research showed that acquiring new customer can cost up to 5 times more than retaining existing ones. However, despite recognizing significance of this aspect, there exist some gaps in understanding of the factors that effect continued usage of PromptPay. Existing literature has explored the impact of satisfaction and emotional engagement on continued usage intention, but to our knowledge, the role of perceived trust and the moderating influence of switching barriers in the context of the PromptPay payment system have not been examined yet. Particularly, the issue of perceived trust becomes a significant concern for persons, who are hesitant to use the service in Thailand. Thus, this research aims to bridge this gap and provide an understanding of the factors influencing the continued usage intentions of the PromptPay system. In this paper, we investigate, how perceived trust influences user satisfaction and their emotional engagement. This study also explores the subsequent impact of these factors on users' intention to continue using PromptPay.

Additionally, we examine, whether switching barriers play a role in influencing users' continued usage intentions.

The thorough analysis of the complex relationships between perceived trust, satisfaction, emotional engagement, switching barriers, and continued usage intention presents a novel contribution to the literature on mobile payment adoption. The findings will offer new insights into the dynamics of user behaviours and preferences in the context of mobile payments in Thailand. Additionally, this research provides relevant insights for policymakers, industry practitioners, and researchers. Policymakers can use these insights to develop regulations and policies that foster a secure and user-friendly mobile payment environment. Industry practitioners can benefit from the findings to enhance PromptPay's user experience, addressing key factors that influence user satisfaction and engagement. Researchers can build on this work to explore additional aspects of mobile payment systems and promote the sustained growth and adoption of PromptPay.

2. Literature Review

The Expectation – Confirmation Theory (ECT)

The expectation–confirmation theory (ECT) is a model that explains the process of user satisfaction and continued usage of a product or service. According to the ECT, users form an initial expectation of the service before using it. After using the service, they have actual experience and compare it with their expectations. If the experience exceeds their expectations, users tend to confirm the use of that service, adopt the usage behavior, and continue to use the service (Joo et al., 2016). On the other hand, the experience might lead to disconfirm or dissatisfaction if what users experience falls below their expectations. The process of confirming or disconfirming expectation is very important to shape users' attitudes and behavior, as this process operates in a recurring cycle.

Perceived Trust

Mayer et al. (1995) defined trust as a willingness to be open to vulnerable as a person believes in positive intentions and actions of others. Kwok et al. (2015) described trust as a level of one's willingness to rely on something based on its ability and reliability. Trust can be explained as a sense of safety and willingness to depend on something (Kim et al., 2011). Thus, trust is the confidence in the reliability, positive intentions, and safety of others or something, leading to a willingness to be vulnerable and depend on it. In terms of perceived trust, Singh and Sinha (2020) defined it as an emotional state fostering that allows someone to trust another based on their behaviour. Perceived trust brings significant advantages to both interpersonal

and business relationships. With perceived trust, people tend to adopt the technology and build a strong relationship with the service. As in case of an online service, persons, who feel comfortable with online transactions, are likely to develop trust to a particular service (Roca et al., 2008). Perceived trust can be considered a key factor in addressing uncertainty and fear. Wong and Mo (2019) also highlighted perceived trust as a key factor that influences customer's intentions to use mobile payments.

The Effect of Perceived Trust on Satisfaction and Emotional Engagement

Amin et al. (2022) defined satisfaction as “user's favourable feeling about the service”. Li and Yeh (2009) also stated that satisfaction is an affective consumer condition from a comprehensive evaluation of all aspects creating consumer relationship. It can be understood as how customers feel about someone, or something based on their experience as customers. Some scholars defined satisfaction as the result of comparing the difference between expectations and actual performance (Liua et al., 2011; Rahman et al., 2017). When the performance meets or exceeds expectations, it leads to satisfaction. On the other hand, if the performance is below expectations, it leads to dissatisfaction.

Engagement represents a complex concept often described as an active participation, an energy in action, and an active involvement (Kanaparan et al., 2019; Park et al., 2012; Sagayadevan & Jeyaraj, 2012). Engagement happens, when persons invest their energy, thoughts, effort, and emotion into what they do (Hewson, 2018). In the world of user experience and relationship, emotional engagement can refer to the emotional connection that a user forms to a particular product or service (Ozhan & Kocadere, 2019). Establishing a relationship also contributes to building the emotional engagement (Hewson, 2018).

Trust can create a sense of reliability and security and persons, who perceive high level of trust can feel more assured that their expectations will be met, which on its own can contribute to their satisfactory experience. Trust is considered a good foundation of relationship (Chang et al., 2014). When person trust the service, they are more likely to build the relationship that give them a sense of security and comfort. This emotional assurance enhances a positive connection and makes users feel more willingness to emotionally engage with the service.

The Effect of Satisfaction and Emotional Engagement on Continued Usage Intention

Based on ECT, user's satisfaction is a key factor that influence continued usage intention. When users are satisfied with the service, they are more likely to perceive value from the overall experience. This positive feeling fosters a willingness to continue using the service in the future. In fact, satisfaction plays an important role in shaping users' intention to continue

the usage of the service. Han et al. (2018) Stated that satisfied users actively engage, reducing the need to explore alternatives. This positive experience enhances users' intention to continue the online service. Similarly, when users are emotionally engaged with the service, they tend to develop loyalty. This emotional connection can help increase the willingness to continue the use of the service.

The Effect of Switching Barrier on Continue Usage Intention

Switching barrier has been found to enhance repurchase intentions through the difficulties that deter users from seeking an alternative (Liua et al., 2011). When users feel that switching to other services might be too difficult, they tend to stick with their current service (Vazquez-casielles et al., 2009). A switching barrier can create a sense of commitment and unwillingness to change and makes users more likely to maintain their usage.

3. Hypotheses, Methodology and Data

The research is based on the collected empirical data, which were used to test the following research hypotheses:

- H1: Perceived trust is positively related to satisfaction.
- H2: Perceived trust is positively related to emotional engagement.
- H3: Satisfaction is positively related to continued usage intention.
- H4: Emotional engagement is positively related to continued usage intention.
- H5: Switching barrier is positively related to continued usage intention.

The conceptual model of the hypotheses is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual model

The analytical method used in the research is the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM is suitable for several reasons. First, PLS-SEM is particularly effective for analysing models with multiple hypotheses, as it does not require strict assumptions about data distribution, which enhances its flexibility for exploratory research. Second, this method is well-suited for evaluating complex models that include multiple-item variables, as it is the case in this study, as it allows to efficiently manage high complexity by integrating both reflective and formative measurement models. Third, PLS-SEM reduces measurement errors, which makes it especially beneficial for the analysis of the data that is not normally distributed, since it does not depend on the assumption of multivariate normality. Fourth, PLS-SEM performs well with small sample sizes, and is able to deliver valid and reliable results. In addition, PLS-SEM focuses on maximizing the explained variance of dependent constructs, which is crucial for the development of a theory and its testing. Lastly, it enables the simultaneous estimation of structural and measurement models, and thus, offers a comprehensive approach to the model assessment.

The sampling frame of this research represents persons, who registered PromptPay service, who have their residence in Bangkok, Thailand. The sample of respondents was selected based on the non-probability method. In particular, convenience sampling method was used to select the sample of respondents in the Bangkok area. However, while convenience sampling is useful for quick data collection, it still has limitations. It can lead to selection bias, making the sample less representative. Additionally, it can introduce a risk of subjectivity as respondents are chosen based on ease of access. To address this, we try to improve representativeness by collecting data from geographical diversity within the Bangkok area. The data collection spanned across three distinct areas: the city centre, mid-range zones, and

suburban districts. The data was collected through the NIDA Poll, a reputable polling organization in Thailand in Spring 2024 (March 1 to April 30, 2024). NIDA Poll employed a sample size of 150 respondents and all responses were used for the analysis. Table 1 summarises the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of respondents

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender	Male	68	45.33
	Female	82	54.67
Age	Under 20 years old	11	7.33
	20 - 26 years old	30	20.00
	27 - 42 years old	44	29.33
	43 - 58 years old	39	26.00
	59 - 77 years old	24	16.00
	over 77 years old	2	1.33
	Educational Level	Elementary School	22
High school		54	36.00
Diploma		36	24.00
Bachelor's		32	21.33
Master's		4	2.67
Higher than Master's		2	1.33

Source: NIDA Poll survey

Based on the survey data, the usage patterns of PromptPay among respondents showed varying levels of engagement with the service. Specifically, 36% of respondents use PromptPay regularly, which indicates a strong foundation of loyal users. However, a significant proportion of respondents (29.3%) use PromptPay randomly, which suggests a less frequent or planned approach to its use. Meanwhile, 20% of respondents use PromptPay only occasionally, which suggests a moderate level of engagement, where users perceive it as beneficial but not necessary for their daily transactions.

However, 9.3% of respondents know about the service, but never used it, which shows a segment of the respondents that has not adopted the service. Additionally, 6% of respondents are categorized as inactive, having used PromptPay in the past, but not using it anymore. For inactive users, the data shows that there are several reasons for discontinuing the use of the PromptPay service. Some reported that they no longer needed the service, while others mentioned having insufficient money in their account registered with the service. Additionally,

a few respondents claimed the preference of cash payments over the PromptPay. The privacy and risk of personal information leak were also mentioned as a concern for their decision to stop using the service. Figure 2 shows the proportion of respondents based on the frequency of their PromptPay service use.

Figure 2 Distribution of respondents based on the frequency of the PromptPay usage

We use the 5-point Likert scale to measure respondents' opinion. This scale ranges from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree), allowing for the evaluation of attitudes and perceptions. The Likert scale was selected due to its simplicity, reliability, and a widespread use in social science research. It provides a standardized method for quantifying qualitative responses and facilitating subsequent statistical analysis.

Perceived Trust is studied through three questions following Kim et al. (2011). The answers are evaluated using the Likert scale. The wording was slightly modified to better align with the context (i.e., “*PromptPay services have integrity,*” “*PromptPay services are reliable,*” “*PromptPay services are trustworthy.*”

Satisfaction is measured using three questions following Puriwat and Tripopsakul (2021). The answers are evaluated using the Likert scale. The wording was slightly modified to better align with the context (i.e., “*I feel satisfied with using PromptPay services,*” “*I feel comfortable using PromptPay service,*” “*I feel contented with using PromptPay service*”).

Emotional Engagement is assessed following Lim et al. (2019). There are four questions using the Likert scale. The statements were adapted to align with the context of the PromptPay (i.e., “*I share my experience or what I think on PromptPay usage with my friends, colleagues, and acquaintances,*” “*I share my opinion regardless if positive or negative with my friends, colleagues and acquaintances,*” “*I share the news or information about PromptPay with*

my friends, colleagues, and acquaintances,” “I expressed my feelings about PromptPay’s payment process and experience”).

Switching Barrier is measured using two questions adapted from Liu et al. (2011). The answers are evaluated using the Likert scale. The wording of the statements was slightly changed to fit the context of our research (i.e., “*Switching to other providers will bring me additional cost,*” “*Switching to other provider will bring psychological burden*”).

Continued Usage Intention is measured by using the approach of Puriwat and Tripopsakul (2021). There are two statements using the Likert scale, i.e., “*I intend to continue using PromptPay services rather than discontinue their use,*” “*I will frequently use PromptPay services in the future,*”

Recognizing the potential influence of demographic factors on formation of trust, we used education level as a control variable. Higher levels of education are associated with greater digital literacy, which help increase understanding of financial technology (Amnas et al., 2024). A study from Wang et al. (2024) found that educational level has a significant impact on the adoption of fintech service. This understanding might affect their trust in such services as PromptPay, which may impact their satisfaction, emotional connection, and continued usage intentions. Moreover, educated users are more aware of benefits of this kind of services. By controlling for education, this study can better analyse users’ experience and understanding how they are affected by educational differences.

4. Results

Validity and reliability

To establish the validity and reliability of measurement prior to hypothesis testing we evaluated the psychometric properties of the scale instruments. Convergent validity, a key aspect of constructs validity, was assessed through factor analysis. Table 2 presents factor loadings for key construct in the study: Perceived trust, Satisfaction, Emotional engagement, Switching barrier, and Continued usage intention. In general, factor loadings exhibit high values, which indicates strong relationships between the measured variables and their respective latent constructs. This suggests that the measurement model for these constructs demonstrates adequate reliability and validity, which provides a solid foundation for subsequent structural model analysis. Factor loadings exceeding 0.5 were considered indicative of adequate convergent validity, signifying that the items within each factor converged to measure the underlying construct effectively. All values exceeded 0.5, which is indicative of adequate convergent validity.

Second, we assessed discriminant validity to ensure the constructs were distinct from other measured variables. Discriminant validity was evaluated by comparing the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) for the correlations between each variable. A well-established criterion suggests that the AVE should exceed all correlations involving the particular construct. This indicates that the variance in the measure of trust is primarily attributable to the construct itself, rather than shared variance with other constructs. The AVE values for each construct in Table 3 are higher than the correlations with other constructs. This demonstrates that each construct shares more variance with its own indicators than with other constructs, confirming the discriminant validity of the measurement model. In other words, the constructs are empirically distinct from one another.

Third, internal consistency reliability of the scale instruments for each construct was established through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability coefficients, presented in Table 4. Fornell and Bookstein (1982) suggested that the acceptable value is above 0.7, which indicates that the items within each scale measure their respective constructs in a consistent manner. In our sample, most of the values are above 0.7.

Table 2 Factor Loadings

Items	Perceived Trust	Satisfaction	Emotional Engagement	Switching Barrier	Continue Usage Intention
PT1	0.918				
PT2	0.942				
PT3	0.910				
SA1		0.821			
SA2		0.904			
SA3		0.932			
EE1			0.873		
EE2			0.901		
EE3			0.911		
EE4			0.706		
SWB1				0.905	
SWB2				0.905	
CUI1					0.862
CUI2					0.862

Note: PT=Perceived Trust, SA= Satisfaction, EE= Emotional Engagement, SWB=Switching Barrier, CUI= Continue Usage Intention

Table 3 *Correlations among Latent Variable with Square Roots of Average Variance Extract (AVE)*

	Perceived Trust	Satisfaction	Emotional Engagement	Switching Barrier	Continue Usage Intention	Gender	Age	Edu
Perceived Trust	0.923							
Satisfaction	0.699	0.887						
Emotional Engagement	0.461	0.445	0.852					
Switching Barrier	0.453	0.438	0.539	0.905				
Continue Usage Intention	0.490	0.574	0.468	0.489	0.862			
Gender	-0.214	-0.217	-0.361	0.010	-0.150	1.00		
Age	-0.065	-0.002	-0.079	0.026	-0.072	0.141	1.00	
Edu	-0.009	0.104	-0.006	0.030	0.169	-0.102	-0.043	1.00

Note: Edu= Educational Lev

Table 4 Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability Coefficients

	Perceived Trust	Satisfaction	Emotional Engagement	Switching Barrier	Continue Usage Intention
Cronbach's Alpha	0.913	0.863	0.870	0.779	0.654
Composite Reliability Coefficients	0.945	0.917	0.913	0.900	0.852

Model Estimation Results

Figure 3 summarizes the findings from PLS-SEM analysis. Hypothesis 1 proposed a positive relationship between perceived trust and satisfaction, indicating that higher levels of trust lead to increased user satisfaction. The result of the analysis is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.704$; $p < 0.001$), thus, the hypothesis 1 is supported. Hypothesis 2 proposed a positive relationship between perceived trust and emotional engagement, suggesting that trust fosters positive emotional connections with the service. The result is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.472$; $p < 0.001$), thus, the hypothesis 2 is supported. Hypothesis 3 proposed a positive relationship between satisfaction and continued usage intention, indicating that satisfied users are more likely to continue using PromptPay. The result is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.336$; $p < 0.001$), thus, the hypothesis 3 is supported. Hypothesis 4 proposed a positive relationship between emotional engagement and continued usage intention, suggesting that emotional connection with the service drives continued usage intention. The result is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.206$; $p = 0.005$), thus, the hypothesis 4 is supported. Hypothesis 5 proposed a positive relationship between switching barriers and continued usage intention, suggesting that higher switching barriers increase the possibility of continued usage intention. The result is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.168$; $p = 0.017$), thus, the hypothesis 5 is supported.

Figure 1 Results from the hypotheses testing

Notes: β = beta (coefficients of the predictors)

p = P-Value (probability value)

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The analysis provided the results that are aligned with the proposed hypotheses. First, the analysis confirmed that the persons, who have a higher level of perceived trust, are more likely to gain more satisfaction level and develop more emotional engagement with the use of the PromptPay service. Our research confirmed that trust provides a foundation upon which user satisfaction and emotional engagement are built (Chang et al., 2014). When users perceive PromptPay as a trustworthy service, they are more likely to develop positive feelings and beliefs about it. This finding is aligned with the existing research, where trust is recognized as a critical factor influencing user satisfaction (Beyari, 2020). Trustworthy service can foster a sense of confidence and peace of mind among users. The positive user perception ultimately leads to greater satisfaction and emotional engagement with the service.

In addition, our analysis showed that the respondents more satisfied with the service and greater level of emotional engagement tend to continue using the service. Satisfied users, who enjoy using PromptPay, are more likely to integrate it into their regular financial routines. Similarly, the users, who develop an emotional connection with the service, perhaps, due to its ease of use or perceived benefits, are more interested in its continued usage.

Moreover, the study found a positive relationship between switching barriers and continued usage intention. This suggests that those users, who perceive high switching barriers, such as difficulty in transferring data or fees, are more likely to continue using PromptPay. This finding is aligned with the research highlighting the role of inertia in user behaviour (Vazquez-casielles et al., 2009), where the perceived difficulty of switching from a service can act as a restraint, even if users are not necessarily highly satisfied with the service.

The use of educational level as a control variable also provided some interesting insights. The findings suggest that higher levels of education may be associated with a greater tendency for continued PromptPay usage. This could be attributed to such factors as higher digital literacy and awareness among more educated users, allowing them to readily understand the benefits and functionalities of the service. Conversely, lower education levels might become challenges for users in navigating the platform or understanding its advantages, potentially discouraging continued usage.

In a more general context, the findings of our study provide empirical support for core principles of ECT in the context of mobile payment adoption. Those users, who perceive PromptPay as a trustworthy service, develop positive expectations about its functionality, security, etc. When these expectations are confirmed through a positive user experience,

satisfaction and emotional engagement, users are more likely to continue using PromptPay. This research extends the application of ECT by demonstrating its relevance for understanding user behaviour of the mobile payment systems. It highlights the importance of building trust and exceeding user expectations to foster a loyal user base for mobile payment services.

This study is also relevant for policy makers, since it provides insights relevant for government and such stakeholders as banks and business. By understanding the key drivers of user satisfaction, emotional engagement, and continued usage intention, PromptPay service providers and other mobile payment platforms can promote a loyal user base. Although fostering trust, satisfaction, and emotional engagement remains crucial, considering strategies that increase switching barriers (such as loyalty programs) to enhance user lock-in and maintaining a user-friendly experience is also crucial.

The study has also some limitations. First, the data collection focused only on respondents in Bangkok, Thailand, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other area contexts because PromptPay usage patterns and influencing factors might differ due to demographics and differences in the infrastructure. Additionally, the used sample size of respondents is satisfactory for exploratory analysis only. The used sampling method does not provide representative sample of the Bangkok population, which further limits the venerability of the results. Larger sample and the use of different sampling method would allow to achieve more robust and statistically significant results. Furthermore, the research only explored the influence of perceived trust, satisfaction, emotional engagement, switching barriers, and education level on continued usage intention. Other factors such as a design of the user interface, perceived security risks, or marketing strategies might also play a role in the decision on the continued usage intention. Also, in the analysis, we used only three control variables, a wider range of control variables could provide deeper understanding of Promptpay user behaviour.

Thus, future research could provide further insights into the specific factors influencing user expectations of PromptPay. Also, exploring the long-term impact of expectation confirmation on user loyalty and advocacy for the service could provide valuable insights. The research on how different demographic segments influence the relationship between confirmation of user expectations and continued usage could help to identify effective strategies for PromptPay providers to attract users. Addressing these research questions would lead to a more comprehensive understanding of user behaviours in the evolving mobile payment landscape.

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Appendix - Questionnaire

Topic PromptPay: Are they really “Prompt (พร้อม - ready)” to continue?

The Mystery of Continuous Usage Intention through Perceived Trust

Explanation: This survey is used to analyze the impact of perceived trust on continue usage intention of person living in Bangkok who register PromptPay service. This survey consists of 5 pages, with 5 sections as follows:

Section 1 Registration status 1 item

Section 2 Demographic information of respondents 7 items

Section 3 Questions for persons who registered PromptPay but never use 2 items

Section 4 Question for persons who Previously used but currently discontinued 2 items

Section 5 Main questions 14 items

In total, there are 9-24 questions (depends on frequency of use of respondents). Personal information of the participants will be kept confidential and not disclosed to the public on an individual basis. The research results will be reported only in the form of summary data.

Section 1 Registration status

Please mark the box with a ✓ that corresponds to your most strongly held opinion.

1. Have you registered PromptPay? Yes No (end of questionnaire)

Section 2 Demographic information of respondents

Please mark the box with a ✓ that corresponds to your most strongly held opinion.

1. Gender Male Female Others
2. Marital status Single Married Others
3. Age Under 20 years old 20-26 years old 27-42 years old
 43-58 years old 59-77 years old over 77 years old
4. Education Elementary School High school Diploma Bachelor's
 Master's Higher than Master's
5. Income per month Below 15,000 Baht 15,001-30,000 baht 30,001-
50,000 baht 50,001-100,000 baht Over 100,000 baht
6. Which method have you used for registration?
 Phone number National ID Both

7. How often do you use PromptPay

- Regular** (Every day to 3-5 times a week) – **please continue at section 5**
- Sometimes** (4-10 times a month) – **please continue at section 5**
- Random** (Less than 4 times a month) – **please continue at section 5**
- Inactive** (Previously used but currently discontinued) – **please continue at section 4 and 5**
- Never** (registered but never use) – **please continue at section 3**

Section 3 Questions for persons who registered PromptPay but never use

Please mark the box with a ✓ that corresponds to your most strongly held opinion.

1. What is/are the reason(s) that you never use the service?

- I don't need it
- I don't trust it
- It's too difficult to use
- I have no idea how it works
- I prefer using cash
- I don't have Smartphone
- I don't have money in the account registered with PromptPay
- I don't want other to know my personal information
- I prefer using other digital payment
- Other (please specify)

2. Do you have any plan to use the service within 3 months?

- Yes
- No
- Will consider

(End of questionnaire)

Section 4 Question for persons who Previously used but currently discontinued

Please mark the box with a ✓ that corresponds to your most strongly held opinion.

1. What is/are the reason(s) that you never use the service?

- I don't need it
- I found it's not useful
- I prefer using cash
- I prefer using other digital payment
- I don't trust it after using it
- It's too hard to use
- I don't have Smartphone now
- I don't have money in the account registered with PromptPay
- I don't want other to know my personal information
- Other (please specify)

2. Do you have any plan to use the service within 3 months?

- Yes
- No
- Will consider

(please continue at section 5)

Section 5 Main questions

Please mark the box with a ✓ that corresponds to your most strongly held opinion.

Perceived Trust

	Please evaluate your team from the following questions, indicating whether you agree or disagree to what extent.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	PromptPay services have integrity.					
2	PromptPay services are reliable.					
3	PromptPay services are trustworthy.					

Satisfaction

	Please evaluate your team from the following questions, indicating whether you agree or disagree to what extent.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I feel satisfied with using PromptPay service.					
2	I feel comfortable using PromptPay service.					
3	I feel contented with using PromptPay service.					

Emotional Engagement

	Please evaluate your team from the following questions, indicating whether you agree or disagree to what extent.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I share my experience or what I think on PromptPay usage with my friends, colleagues, and acquaintances.					
2	I share my opinion regardless if positive or negative with my friends, colleagues and acquaintances.					
3	I share the news or information about PromptPay with my friends, colleagues, and acquaintances.					
4	I am interested in staying updated on news or developments related to PromptPay.					

Switching Barrier

	Please evaluate your team from the following questions, indicating whether you agree or disagree to what extent.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Switching to other providers will bring additional cost.					
2	Switching to other provider will bring psychological burden.					

Continue Usage Intention

	Please evaluate your team from the following questions, indicating whether you agree or disagree to what extent.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I intend to continue using PromptPay service rather than discontinue their use in the future.					
2	I expect to use PromptPay more frequently in the future.					

Do you have any comments regarding the use of PromptPay? Please feel free to share us below

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